

Comprehensive Overview of Food Contamination Across Various Processing Stages

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Abstract

Food contamination can arise from various circumstances, as elucidated in this paper. It offers a comprehensive analysis detailing the diverse stages involved in food processing, beginning from the receipt of raw materials to the eventual consumption of food by end consumers.

Among the factors contributing to food contamination processes, the following key elements merit attention: a) External contamination of raw food stemming from environmental pollutants. b) Transportation of raw materials to the processing facility. c) Food preparation, encompassing raw material storage, preheating, disinfection, cleaning, and sterilization procedures. d) Application of heat through boiling, cooking, baking, frying, or high-temperature blending with other ingredients, either in ovens or reactors. e) Packaging of food products. f) Transporting packaged food items. g) Storage and distribution of packaged food products. The challenges associated with each stage, alongside the contaminants generated in the food, are meticulously delineated and analyzed.

Keywords: Food contamination, Food process, Raw food, Heating, Packaging.

A) INTRODUCTION

Research has unequivocally shown that food contamination, whether microbiological or chemical in nature, remains the paramount concern for consumers. Consequently, there is an ongoing endeavor to delve deeper into the sources of contamination and explore effective prevention measures. Considerable effort has been directed towards the development of analytical methodologies capable of detecting and identifying these contaminants, as they typically occur in trace amounts. Sample treatment devices, such as micro-extraction techniques, have been devised to eliminate matrix interferences and concentrate analytes from the sample, presenting robust tools for food analysis. However, the task of identifying contaminants, whether originating from food production, processing, or packaging, remains a formidable challenge. Different analytical tools have been developed to facilitate the task, but none of them provide a unique solution. When the probable contaminants are identified, targeted analysis becomes more viable, albeit the low concentrations necessitate the utilization of sample treatment techniques and sophisticated analytical instruments. However, untargeted analysis, in which the contaminants are unknown, poses a significant challenge, underscoring the crucial role of screening procedures. Within this context, the utilization of sample treatment techniques in conjunction with high-resolution mass spectrometry furnishes the robust tools necessary for identifying unknown contaminants. Consequently, acquiring information about the probable contaminants originating from each stage of food processing is indispensable. In the following

paragraphs the description of the main contaminants in each step, how to control them and how to prevent or diminish them from the food are discussed. This information is imperative for pinpointing the source of contaminants present in the final food product.

B) Exploring the critical stages of food processing

External sources of raw food contamination

Certain chemicals may already be present in raw food at the onset of food processing, owing to environmental contamination. The expansion of industries, advancements in agrochemical utilization, and urban activities all contribute to the presence of contaminants in food. A significant concern regarding food contaminants lies in the use of fertilizers and pesticides, as their consumption can lead to health issues in humans. Several studies have detected residues of pesticides in fruits and vegetable[1, 2]. Furthermore, derivatives with adverse effects, such as metabolites from organochlorine pesticides, have also been discovered in fatty food sources[2]. The application of fertilizers and pesticides is also presumed to be the primary contributor to the release of toxic heavy metals. Heavy metals such as cadmium, lead, mercury, and arsenic are well-acknowledged for their toxic properties, (can be present in air, soil, and water) and therefore they can be transferred to foodstuff[3]. The analysis of heavy metals has been conducted in various food items, including honey, spinach, potatoes, fish, and tea. Major techniques utilized for heavy metal analysis include flame atomic absorption spectrometry (FAAS),

graphite furnace atomic absorption spectrometry (GFAAS), cold vapor atomic absorption spectrometry (CVAAS), inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectrometry (ICP-AES), and inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS)[4]. Antibiotic residues constitute another extensively studied area in food safety. They are commonly used in animal farming, yet without proper quality control, they can persist as residues in food products. These residues pose potential harm to humans if ingested in significant quantities. Numerous methods have been devised to detect antibiotic residues in food items such as meat, eggs, or milk. These methods include the microbial inhibition plate test, as well as liquid chromatography techniques[5, 6]. Preventing external sources of raw food contamination is crucial in ensuring the safety of our food supply. One way to reduce the risk of contamination is by thoroughly washing all fruits and vegetables before consumption. This can help remove any dirt, pesticides, or bacteria that may be present on the surface of the produce. Another important step is to properly store raw foods at the correct temperature to prevent the growth of harmful bacteria[7].

Contamination risks during food transport

Food contamination can occur during transportation, stemming from vehicle exhaust emissions of petrol and diesel, or as a result of cross-contamination within the vehicles utilized for food transportation. This cross-contamination poses a significant risk to food safety. In 1999, a significant illness outbreak in the European Economic Community was linked to fungicide-contaminated pallets utilized for the transportation and storage of food packaging materials. Additionally, long-distance transport ships have been affected multiple times by cross-contamination from chemicals used for disinfection or originating from other sources[2, 8]. The primary issue arises from the fact that high barrier materials typically used for wrapping and safeguarding food during prolonged transportation, such as by ship, are not consistently evaluated for their barrier properties against organic compounds. Typically, only permeation by permanent gases like O₂, CO₂, and water vapor is assessed, overlooking the permeability to organic compounds. The study conducted by [researcher name or organization] serves as a pertinent example, demonstrating the contamination of food through the permeation of naphthalene, methyl bromide, toluene, ethylbenzene, as well as ortho- and para-xylene, through a theoretically high barrier material[9, 10]. Regular inspections and audits of transportation processes can help identify potential risks and areas for improvement. By implementing these strategies, food businesses can minimize the risks of contamination during transport and ensure that their products reach consumers safely and in compliance with food safety regulations[11].

Contamination risks associated with cleaning processes

Cleaning and disinfection procedures during food processing play a critical role in eliminating potential microorganisms and thus are essential for reducing food contamination. It is imperative that chemicals employed as cleaners or disinfectants are suitable for contact with food surfaces and are compliant with regulatory standards. Certain products like glass or certain metal cleaners cannot be utilized as they may leave hazardous residues. Moreover, the excessive use of sanitizers may result in residual concentrations on treated materials or food, even in minimally processed fruits and

vegetables. Hence, quantifying the residual chemicals present in food is crucial to ensure their complete removal and compliance with safety standards[12]. Some common surfactants are quaternary ammonium compounds such as dodecyl-trimethyl-ammonium chloride and nonionic surfactants such as stearyl alcohol ethoxylate. Factors affecting its elimination from different materials surfaces, such as rinsing time or water temperature, These compounds are typically analyzed using liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry[2]. Authors have extensively discussed issues related to residues originating from cleaning agents and disinfectants used on surfaces of food handling equipment, as well as their potential transfer to food that has been in contact with such surfaces[13]. The development of safe, efficient, and environmentally friendly detergent formulas is a significant concern for the food industry. Another alternative under consideration is the utilization of ozone, owing to its potent oxidizing properties. Extensive studies have been conducted to ensure adequate levels of quality and safety in its application. Furthermore, a blend of inorganic peroxides has emerged as a potential option for this purpose. However, an additional risk associated with this approach is the rapid oxidation-induced degradation of certain compounds and the formation of new compounds resulting from the interaction between food components and disinfection reagents. Emerging technologies such as electrical pulses, high pressures, or beta and gamma irradiation on food present new avenues. In these technologies, it is imperative to thoroughly investigate the transformation of nutrients and food components, as well as the formation of newly generated compounds[14, 15]. To minimize contamination risks during cleaning processes, it is crucial to implement thorough training for employees on proper cleaning techniques and hygiene practices. Establishing clear protocols and procedures for cleaning equipment and surfaces can help reduce the likelihood of cross-contamination. Additionally, using designated cleaning tools and supplies for specific areas can prevent the spread of harmful bacteria. Regular monitoring and auditing of cleaning practices can ensure that standards are being met consistently[16]. Implementing a system for reporting any issues or concerns related to cleanliness can help address potential risks promptly. By prioritizing cleanliness and following strict guidelines, businesses can effectively minimize food contamination risks associated with cleaning processes[17].

Contamination risks during heating steps

Heating treatment stands as the predominant method for food processing, both within the industry and at home, given that approximately 80-90% of consumed food undergoes some form of processing. The employment of high cooking temperatures, coupled with external factors, can result in the generation of toxic compounds, posing a potential threat to food quality and safety. Various toxic compounds may form in foods during processing stages such as heating, baking, roasting, grilling, canning, hydrolysis, or fermentation [8]. Frying stands out as the cooking process most capable of generating a diverse array of toxic compounds within the food. Frying operates as a dehydration process wherein oil serves as the medium for heat transfer. Oxidation processes within frying oil are suppressed by the food, particularly by proteins, starch, or phenolic compounds. The interaction between frying fat and protein can lead to the production of mutagenic polycyclic aromatic heterocycles. Oxidation products tend to bind with proteins and other constituents of the substrate. Flavor compounds are generated through

reactions between oxidized frying oil and proteins, as well as other sulfur and nitrogen compounds present in the food. Additionally, a variety of compounds are released from the food into the frying oil, contributing to discoloration or off-flavors. Furthermore, pigments within the frying oil may be absorbed onto the surface of fried food items [18].

An emerging category of heat-induced contaminants, formed when salted food comes into contact with oil at high temperatures, includes chlorophenol fatty acid esters, such as 3-monochloro-1,2-propanediol (3-MCPD) and related substances. These compounds are produced in vegetable oils and edible fats, particularly those subjected to high-temperature deodorization processes. Levels of 3-MCPD can reach up to 14.7 mg/kg, significantly exceeding the Tolerable Daily Intake (TDI). It's noteworthy that infant formula may also contain this compound. Due to their intrinsic toxicity and the observed levels in food, a thorough risk assessment study regarding human exposure to such contaminants is warranted.

According to a recent report from EFSA, the mean exposure to 3-MCPD was less than 1 mg/kg body weight per day in the majority of population groups (60 out of 64 age groups across surveys). Mean dietary exposure ranged from 1 to 1.5 mg/kg body weight per day in four population groups. The 95th percentile (P95) of exposure was below 2 mg/kg body weight per day in 56 population groups and ranged between 2 and 3 mg/kg body weight per day in the remaining eight population groups. 'Margarine and similar products' were identified as the primary contributors to exposure in 45 population groups (70%), while 'Vegetable fats and oils (excluding walnut oil)' accounted for exposure in 18 population groups (28%). Other notable contributors included 'Bread and rolls' (contributing 6-26% to total exposure), 'Fine bakery wares' (4-29%), and 'Preserved meat (smoked)' (3-18%)[19].

Indeed, 3-MCPD can originate from other sources as well. It can be formed during the acid hydrolysis of wheat, soybean, and other vegetable protein products. Additionally, it may migrate from epichlorohydrin resins utilized for humidity protection in paper and cellulose materials, which are often employed for sausage casings.

The majority of analytical methods (>95%) reported for this compound utilize gas chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry (GC-MS), while a smaller proportion (5%) employ high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC). It is recommended to further develop and establish standard analytical methods for analyzing 3-MCPD to reduce uncertainty in occurrence and exposure estimates[8, 19].

Acrylamide and its precursors represent significant contaminants arising from heating processes. Acrylamide is a reactive substance believed to be genotoxic and carcinogenic based on animal studies. It predominantly forms in starchy and carbohydrate-rich foods, such as French fries, during high-temperature food processing (>120°C). These contaminants are released from the crust due to water vapor escaping as steam, limited by the crust's porosity or the matrix's capillary structure.

The formation of acrylamide depends on several factors, with heat transfer being paramount, influenced by temperature, heat

conductivity of the heating medium (air, fat, water), heating duration, water activity, pH, and concentrations of amino and carbonyl reactants. The transfer of fat to and from the substrate into the frying fat relies on the food's fat content and frying conditions. Polar compounds, like pigments, migrate into the frying oil.

Precursors of these contaminants can naturally occur in the food matrix, such as acrylamide formed during the Maillard reaction between asparagine and reducing sugars, especially in potato- and cereal-based heat-treated products. However, acrylamide is also a monomer with specific migration limits (SML) regulated by food contact plastics legislation. Surprisingly, the concentration of acrylamide in foods derived from heated cereal derivatives exceeds the established SML. Significant efforts have been devoted to reducing acrylamide in these foodstuffs after discovering that food processing was the primary source of this compound in many products. Lowering processing temperatures has been shown to decrease acrylamide concentrations. Additionally, both frying and oven heating, with or without air, contribute to enhanced acrylamide formation[12, 19].

The prevailing analytical methods for acrylamide typically follow a similar protocol: solid-phase extraction, followed by determination using either gas chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry (GC/MS) after bromination, or direct measurement with liquid chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry (LC/MS). These methods demonstrate consistent agreement and are expected to be accurate, offering comparable limits of detection (LOD) and limits of quantification (LOQ)[20].

Certain processing contaminants, such as nitrosamines, can arise from the interaction of natural food components with food additives during heating processes. For instance, nitroso dimethylamine has been identified in specific foods due to direct-fire drying or roasting methods. In such cases, nitrogen oxides present in the drying air react with amines in the food during heating. Nitroso dimethylamine is the most prevalent volatile nitrosamine found in food, although nitroso pyrrolidine is also detected, albeit to a lesser extent.

Cured meats are another source of nitrosamines because meat contains amines, and sodium nitrite, a nitrosating agent, is commonly added to cured meats as a preservative. Bacon typically contains detectable levels of nitrosamines, primarily nitrosopyrrolidine, and to a lesser extent, dimethyl nitrosamine. It's worth noting that nitrosamine formation during vapor or boiling cooking methods, which involve lower temperatures (around 100°C), is generally lower compared to frying, roasting, or grilling.

Nitrosamines can be measured using various methodologies, including colorimetric and spectroscopic methods following gas or liquid chromatography, or by assessing total N-nitroso groups through the measurement of chemically released nitric oxide. Gas chromatography (GC) coupled with a specific thermal energy analyzer detector (TEA) is considered the most suitable, sensitive, and widely used analytical method for detecting volatile nitrosamines. The complex matrix of food samples and the low concentrations expected of the studied analytes make it necessary to include isolation and preconcentration steps in the analytical procedure[21-23].

Additional processing contaminants formed during heating include polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), which are found in grilled and smoked products, as well as ethyl carbamate and furan derivatives present in various heat-treated foods, particularly coffee and canned/jarred products. Furan contributes to the off-flavor of food and can be formed from various precursors, including ascorbic acid, degradation of carbohydrates, degradation of amino acids, and oxidation of fatty acids[24]. The production of mutagens is significantly reduced in the absence of fat. Model mixtures containing Maillard precursors such as glycine, glucose, and creatinine were heated in the presence of iron salts and fats. Consequently, substituted imidazoquinoxalines were identified among the mutagenic products. The reaction was intensified by oxidized fats and iron salts, with no inhibition observed from tocopherol. Additionally, some mutagenic activity of frying fats originates from nitrogen-free lipid-hydroperoxide decomposition products, which are unrelated to the fried substrate. These products arise solely from the oxidation of oxidized and polymerized triacylglycerols or free fatty acids[2, 19].

Microwave heating is rapidly gaining popularity as a method for heating foodstuffs both in households and in certain industrial sectors. Over the past decade, a diverse range of foods has been developed and tailored for the microwave market. A notable characteristic of microwave cooking is that the food is cooked within its packaging material, such as wrapping film or containers, inside the microwave oven. Microwavable packaging materials encompass various substances such as plastics, paperboard, and composites[25]. During microwave cooking, many components of these materials, including plasticizers, antioxidants, monomers, stabilizers, and others, have the potential to migrate from the package into the food. This migration can lead to a decline in both food quality and safety[26]. During microwave heating, high temperatures are frequently attained within short durations. Microwaves have the ability to accelerate diffusion rates, induce degradation of migrants or polymers, and generate hot spots within the food or packaging material[19]. These factors can result in migration levels surpassing those anticipated from the bulk heating temperature alone. The extent of migration hinges on various factors including heating time, microwave power setting, the composition of the food, and the initial concentration of the migrant within the packaging material[19, 26]. Contamination during heating steps can have a significant impact on the quality and safety of the final product. One of the main concerns is the potential introduction of harmful bacteria or pathogens into the product, which can lead to foodborne illnesses or other health risks for consumers. This is especially true for products that are not cooked at high enough temperatures to kill off these contaminants[27]. Furthermore, practicing good personal hygiene by washing hands frequently and wearing clean gloves when handling food can help prevent contamination during heating steps. By implementing these strategies, you can reduce the risk of contamination during the heating process and ensure that your food remains safe for consumption[28].

Contamination risks during food packaging

In modern times, the majority of food is sold within packaging. Food packaging offers numerous benefits including physical protection, barrier protection, and enhanced food preservation, thereby extending the shelf life of the product. During the manufacturing of food packaging, various additives such as antioxidants, stabilizers, slipping

agents, or plasticizers are often incorporated into the polymers to enhance material properties. However, the direct or indirect contact between the food and the packaging material can result in the transfer of these substances from the packaging to the food, a phenomenon known as migration, migrants from packaging materials can potentially pose health risks to consumers if they exhibit toxic effects[29]. When metallic cans are utilized for food packaging, corrosion on the metallic surface of the can may lead to the migration of metallic ions into the food, such as iron or tin. To mitigate this risk, the internal side of metallic cans is often coated with varnishes such as epoxy resins to protect them from corrosion. However, minor by-products from the manufacture of epoxy resins, such as bisphenol A, bisphenol A diglycidyl ether (BADGE), or cyclo-di-BADGE, among others, can migrate into the food. These compounds have been identified as endocrine disruptors.

Another common material used in packaging for products like marmalades, jams, vegetables, beans, or sauces is glass. In this scenario, migration occurs from the metallic lids used to seal the glass jars. These lids typically feature a PVC gasket to ensure a tight seal. Epoxidized soybean oil (ESBO) is one of the additives used as a plasticizer in PVC, and its migration into food has been reported by several authors[19, 30].

Paper and board are frequently employed for packaging dry food items such as flour or sugar, as well as products like rice, cereals, or frozen food. Migration from additives in paperboard or from printing inks to foodstuffs can occur. It's worth noting that paper is the most recycled packaging material, and the use of recycled materials can potentially lead to food contamination from substances such as mineral oils or plasticizers originating from printing inks or adhesives[19, 30].

Typical polymers utilized in food packaging materials include polyethylene (PE), high-density polyethylene (HDPE), polyethylene terephthalate (PET), polyvinyl chloride (PVC), polystyrene (PS), and polycarbonate (PC). The selection of material depends on the specific application requirements. Moreover, these polymers can also be combined in multilayer structures to enhance the overall packaging properties. Within these polymers, various substances may be added to improve their characteristics, such as UV filters, antioxidants, plasticizers, or colorants. It's important to note that all of these additives have the potential to migrate into the packaged food[31].

Multilayer materials can incorporate various polymers as well as adhesive layers, printing inks, or varnishes. Migration may occur from all these components, even if they are not in direct contact with the food, due to diffusion and partition processes of migrants. Numerous studies have examined migration from different types of adhesives commonly used in food packaging, including acrylic, hot-melt, rubber, or polyurethane adhesives[2, 31]. Migration from inks has also been extensively researched, particularly the migration of photo initiators such as benzophenone (BP) or 2-isopropylthioxanthone (ITX) originating from UV-curable inks. Additionally, more recent studies have reported migration from components found in printing inks as a result of set-off transference[2]. Recycled plastic materials hold special significance as they may contain chemical compounds from previously packaged food, substances resulting from consumer

misuse of the packaging, or intrinsic contaminants from the recycling process such as chemical additives[32].

Ensuring food safety is crucial in preventing foodborne illnesses and maintaining consumer confidence. One key aspect of ensuring food safety is through effective packaging strategies. Packaging plays a vital role in protecting food from contamination, spoilage, and physical damage during transportation and storage. Implementing proper packaging techniques such as using barrier materials to prevent oxygen and moisture from entering the package, incorporating antimicrobial agents to inhibit bacterial growth, and implementing tamper-evident seals to detect any potential breaches are essential in safeguarding the integrity of the food product[33]. Additionally, choosing packaging materials that are non-toxic, resistant to chemicals, and suitable for the specific type of food being packaged is essential in maintaining the quality and safety of the product. By implementing these effective packaging strategies, food producers can ensure that their products reach consumers safely while preserving their freshness and quality[34].

Contamination risks during food storage

Food storage conditions are essential for maintaining both the quality and safety of food products. Factors such as temperature, humidity, and packaging play crucial roles in determining the shelf life and overall condition of stored foods. High temperatures and humidity can adversely affect packaging materials, leading to phenomena such as migration and sorption of substances that may ultimately impact food quality. To prevent organoleptic changes during storage, packaging materials must possess excellent barrier properties, effectively regulating the transfer of gases, aromas, and volatile organic compounds[13, 19].

The interplay between temperature and humidity heavily influences physico-chemical processes, with lower humidity levels preferred to minimize undesired phenomena and prevent the degradation of packaging materials. Optimal storage temperatures typically range from cool to moderate, while exposure to direct sunlight can accelerate deterioration. Certain food items, particularly those high in fat content, are more susceptible to odor contamination during storage[12].

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Different types of foods have varying shelf lives, with dry and canned foods generally lasting longer but experiencing gradual deterioration in color, flavor, and nutritional value over time. Perishable items such as meat, fish, eggs, and dairy products require freezer or refrigerator storage to minimize the risk of contamination[35].

Additionally, the permeability of flexible plastic packaging materials must be carefully evaluated, as it directly impacts the transfer of compounds through the packaging. Previous research has demonstrated the importance of understanding and controlling permeability to ensure the quality and safety of stored food products. When using flexible plastic materials it is also important to evaluate its permeability, since depending on the barrier properties the transference of compounds through the packaging material will be different as was demonstrated [30, 36].

Certain contaminants found in food storage facilities, such as mold and toxins produced by bacteria or fungi, can have detrimental effects on respiratory health when ingested or inhaled. Overall, the potential health risks associated with contaminated food highlight the importance of proper storage practices to prevent contamination and protect consumer health[37].

C. Final Reflections

This study underscores the critical junctures in food processing where contamination can occur, thereby emphasizing its significance in preventing foodborne illnesses and safeguarding consumer health. While certain contaminants may originate from raw materials, others can infiltrate during transportation or processing stages, influenced by factors like cleansing procedures and heating methods. Additionally, food packaging itself can pose a risk through migration phenomena. These findings underscore the necessity of robust chemical analysis throughout food processing to ensure the safety and integrity of food products for consumers.

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